

SEARCH FOR NEW LOCAL ANAESTHETICS. PART IV

BY I. SEN GUPTA, (MISS) HARWANT KAUR AND VASUDEV

Several basic anilides have been synthesised for studying their local anaesthetic activity.

Meyer (*Arch. exper. Path. Pharmacol.*, 1899, 42, 109; 1901, 46, 335) and Overton (*Arch. ges. Physiol.*, 1902, 92, 115) observed that the potency of a local anaesthetic was due to its increased affinity for lipoids. Basic esters, in which the methylene group of the alkylene chain is replaced by a phenylene residue, have been studied by Fellows (*Proc. Soc. Exptl. Biol. Med.*, 1943, 53, 7; *Chem. Abs.*, 1943, 37, 4472), and some of these esters show good local anaesthetic activity. In the present investigation compounds of the general types (I) and (II) have been synthesised, where the alkylene chain connecting lyophilic and hydrophilic moieties has been replaced by a phenylene unit. It is expected that in these compounds the phenylene radical may further anchor the lyophilic moiety. The methoxy and the amino groups (I: R=OMe- and NH₂) *para* to the anaesthesiophoric group have been substituted in view of such groups being present in some known local anaesthetics.

In compounds of the general type (II) the >C=N- group is a polarised group similar to carbonyl group, and further these compounds possess also the necessary structural requirements of a local anaesthetic.

Compounds of the type (I) were obtained by treating *p*-dialkylaminoaniline with an acid chloride (anisic, *p*-toluic and *p*-nitrobenzoic). The nitro compounds were reduced to the corresponding amino derivatives. All the bases were smoothly converted into their hydrochlorides. For the preparation of compounds of the type (II) *p*-dimethylaminoaniline was refluxed with the carbonyl compound (piperonal, vanillin, anisaldehyde, acetophenone and salicylaldehyde) in alcoholic solution. The condensed products were converted into their hydrochlorides.

EXPERIMENTAL

(1). *p*-Toluamido-4-dimethylaniline.—*p*-Aminodimethylaniline (2.7 g., 0.02M) in dry ether (15 c.c.) was treated with *p*-toluoyl chloride (3.7 g., 0.024 M) in dry ether

(15 c.c.). The mixture was heated under reflux for 1 hour and the ether distilled off. The residue was treated with sodium bicarbonate solution. The product was collected, washed with water and crystallised from 90% alcohol in needles, m.p. 250°. (Found: N, 10.9. $C_{18}H_{18}ON_2$ requires N, 11.02%).

The *hydrochloride* of the base was prepared by saturating the solution of the base in absolute alcohol with dry HCl gas. Alcohol was distilled off and the residue crystallised from absolute alcohol, m.p. 262° (decomp.). (Found: N, 9.41. $C_{18}H_{18}ON_2Cl$ requires N, 9.64%).

(2). *p-Nitrobenzamido-4-dimethylaniline*.—*p*-Aminodimethylaniline (2.7 g., 0.02 M) was similarly treated with *p*-nitrobenzoyl chloride (4.5 g., 0.024 M) in ether solution. The nitro compound was crystallised from methyl alcohol in bronze needles, m.p. 257° (cf. Heilbron, "Dictionary of Organic Compounds", 1946, Vol. I, p. 75).

(3). *p-Aminobenzamido-4-dimethylaniline*.—The above nitro compound (3 g.) was added to stannous chloride (10 g.), dissolved in HCl (15 c.c.). The mixture was heated on a water-bath at 80.90° for 5 hours with occasional shaking. The mixture was cooled and treated with 65% NaOH solution (20 c.c.). The precipitated base was collected and washed with water. It was crystallised from dilute alcohol (charcoal) in needles, m.p. 179°.

The *hydrochloride* of the base was prepared in absolute alcohol. It could not be crystallised from any common solvent; however, it was washed thoroughly with dry acetone, absolute alcohol and dry ether, m.p. 252-53° (decomp.). (Found: N, 13.2. $C_{18}H_{17}ON_2 \cdot 2HCl$ requires N, 12.8%).

Other analogous compounds in this series, prepared in a similar manner, are reported in Table I (No. 6 to 10).

(4). *4-Hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene-4-aminodimethylaniline*.—A mixture of vanillin (7.6 g.) and *p*-aminodimethylaniline (6.8 g.) in absolute alcohol (60 c.c.) was heated under reflux for 4 hours. Alcohol was partly distilled off when a solid product separated. It was cooled and the solid mass collected. A further amount of the product was also recovered from the filtrate. The compound was finally recrystallised from alcohol in needles, m.p. 138°.

The *hydrochloride* of the above base was prepared in dry ether and crystallised from absolute alcohol, m.p. 220°. (Found: N, 7.99; Cl, 20.6. $C_{18}H_{18}O_2N_2 \cdot 2HCl$ requires N, 8.1; Cl, 20.7%).

(5). *2'-Hydroxybenzylidene-4-aminodimethylaniline* was similarly prepared by refluxing salicylaldehyde (6.1 g.) with *p*-aminodimethylaniline (6.8 g.) in absolute alcohol. The base came out to be a pasty mass and was therefore converted into its hydrochloride in dry ether, m.p. 171°. (Found: N, 8.8; Cl, 22.5. $C_{18}H_{17}ON_2 \cdot 2HCl$ requires N, 8.9; Cl, 26.6%).

Other analogous compounds prepared in this series are reported in Table I (compounds No. 11 to 13).

TABLE I

No.	Compounds.	Cryst. from	[A stands for aniline.]		Mol. Formula.	Found.	Calc.
			Melting points of the Compound. Hyd ² ochloride.				
6.	<i>p</i> -Anisamido-4-dimethyl-A.	Abs. alcohol	176°	228° (dec.)	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₂	N : 10.50	10.37
7.	<i>p</i> -Nitrobenzamido-4-diethyl-A.	Dil. ..	168°	...	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₃	N : 13.10	13.40
8.	<i>p</i> -Aminobenzamido-4-diethyl-A		206°	262° (dec.)	C ₁₇ H ₂₁ ON ₂	N : 14.68	14.84
9.	<i>p</i> -Toluanido-4-diethyl-A.		129°	245° (dec.)	C ₁₈ H ₂₂ ON ₂	N : 10.20	9.92
10.	<i>p</i> -Anisamido-4-diethyl-A.		146°	234° (dec.)	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ O ₂ N ₂	N : 9.01	9.39
11.	3':4'-Methylenedioxybenzylidene-4 aminodimethyl-A		112°	213°	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂	C : 71.2 H : 5.8 N : 10.4	71.6 5.9 10.4
12.	α -Phenylethylidene-4-aminodimethyl-A.		85°	168°	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ N ₂	N : 11.6	11.7
13.	4'-Methoxybenzylidene-4-aminodimethyl-A.		144°	242°	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ ON ₂	N : 10.87	11.01

Compounds No. 3 and 6 have been tested at the Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow for local anaesthetic activity. None of the compounds have any surface anaesthetic properties in 2% solution according to the method of Chance and Lobstein (*J. Pharmacol.*, 1944, **82**, 203). When tested for intradermal anaesthesia according to the method of Buibring and Wajda (*ibid.*, 1945, **85**, 78) in 2% solution in normal saline, the action started after one minute and lasted for 100 and 65 minutes respectively with inflammatory reaction. The compounds are being further studied for their pharmacological activity.

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DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
PANJAB UNIVERSITY,
ROSHIANPUR.

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